

Terms of Use

For data requests of ‘Study on effectiveness of infant massage intervention “Shantala Babymassage Individueel” for vulnerable families in early life (until the age of child of 5 months)’.

This documents describes the terms of use and instructions for data requests.

Article 1. Description of data (metadata)

1. A description of the collected data is available and registered through:
 - a. ISRCTN trial register: <https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN16929184>
 - b. Open access published protocol paper: Windhorst e.a., 2023; <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-023-04039-z>
2. A description of first findings and the sample description can be found through:
 - a. Scientific poster presented at ISSBD 2024: <https://ris-data.tno.nl/bibliotheek/sv-015068/TNO/Presentaties/2024/windhorst-2024-preventive.pdf>
 - b. Effect paper: in preparation to be published open access
3. The data has been anonymized and is securely stored in the vault of TNO’s sharepoint for 10 years (starting September 2024).

Article 2. Data requests

1. Data requests can be submitted to the research committee by emailing dr. Mariska Klein Velderman at TNO (Mariska.KleinVelderman@tno.nl) with TNO’s Child Health Secretary in cc (ChildHealthSecretary@tno.nl).
2. The data request will be reviewed by the members of the Dutch infant massage intervention “Shantala Babymassage Individueel” quasi-experimental trial research committee (i.e., Dr. M. Klein Velderman, Dr. D. Windhorst, Dr. S. van der Pal, Prof. dr. C. de Weerth).
3. The data request should include:
 - a. Contact information of the applicant
 - b. Introduction/background of the data request
 - c. Overview of requested data
 - d. Data analysis plan which includes a description of the study's purpose, relevant research questions and hypotheses, and appropriate statistical analysis.
 - e. A signed statement that the delivered data will only be used for the proposed analysis plan and that data will be stored securely in accordance with applicable standards and not be used for commercial purposes.
4. After approval, the applicant will receive anonymized data through a secured link.
5. Any costs associated with the data request, or preparation of a Data Transfer Agreement, are coordinated in advance and shall be borne by the applicant.

Article 3. Publication of findings

1. After data transfer, applicants will commit themselves to publish their findings.
2. The research committee will be able to review the findings and will be included as co-authors.